

THE VALUE-BASED ATTITUDE MOTIVATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS TOWARD FUTURE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the process of forming the value attitude of future teachers to professional activity, which will take place in the educational system of higher education institutions, the main part of which is the formation of positive motivation for future work. This is carried out in the process of professional training of a personality, which is primarily associated with the formation of motives for professional activity and the structure of professional knowledge, skills, and abilities. The purpose of the study is to find out the ways of forming a valuable attitude toward future professional activity within the motivational sphere of higher education students' personalities.

Keywords: value-based attitude toward professional activity, motivation, professional training, future teachers, professional establishment of a personality.

The formation of a young specialist's personality is a multifaceted process that results not only in a set of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, but also in the spiritual image of the future teacher, his/her attitude toward the surroundings, the realities of professional activity, and his/her understanding of existential issues of human existence. Nowadays, higher pedagogical schools pay insufficient attention to the rational correlation and interconnection of socio-cultural, educational, professional and personal values of higher education students and adhere to traditional approaches in the organisation of professional training.

In general, a significant contribution to the study of value issues was made by

O. Badiul, V. Baranivskiy, A. Lazaruk, K. Levkivska, L. Pelekh, S. Reznikov, O. Sholokh and others. The theoretical and methodological foundations for the implementation of the axiological approach in the educational process of different types of educational institutions are described in the works of I. Kniazheva, O. Marchenko, V. Ognevnyuk, O. Savchenko, O. Sukhomlynska, T. Varenko and others. The need for value-based content of the educational process in modern educational institutions is substantiated by O. Dubaseniuk, M. Korman, L. Pelekh, E. Yashchenko and other scholars. The axiological foundations of the process of improving teachers' professional activity are analysed in the works of T. Kaliuzhna, L. Khomych, A. Nikora, O. Pavlova, N. Tkachova, etc.

The purpose of the article is to find out the ways of forming a value-based attitude towards future professional activity within the motivational sphere of the personality of a higher education student.

A value-based attitude to future professional activity is formed through the individual's awareness of the significance of this activity, the development of sustainable professional interests, emotional experience of the results of their work, and the cultivation of a desire for active creative work. The formation of positive motivation for future work is carried out in the process of

professional training of a person, which is primarily associated with the formation of motives for professional activity and the structure of professional knowledge, skills and abilities.

The formation of motivation for professional activity is carried out in two directions: the transformation of general personal motives into professional ones, and changes in the system of professional motives, which is associated with changes in the level of professionalisation. The first direction is to acquire knowledge and ideas about the future profession. General motivation is filled with professional content. An individual compares his/her motives with the requirements of the profession and evaluates the profession in terms of meeting his/her needs. The more opportunities the profession provides to meet the needs and interests of a person, the higher the likelihood of engaging in professional activity. A person achieves the highest efficiency in labour activity when the profession becomes personally meaningful.

Another area of motivation formation is the change of motivation at different stages of professional development. Changing the dominant motivation is an individual process that depends on personal qualities, working conditions, training, and organisation of activities.

The educational process of a higher education institution is both an environment and a stage of professional training. The emergence, formation, actualisation or change of motivation of a future teacher occurs here – in the process of professional training. If motivation involves the satisfaction of personal needs, then the value attitude towards future professional activity is determined by the extent to which these needs coincide with the requirements of the profession.

The value attitude to future professional activity within the motivational sphere of the personality of a higher education student – a future professional – has certain characteristics.

The most important thing in the formation of motivation is the fact that in early youth, special internal

conditions are formed that put it at the centre of mental development – a change in the internal position, and achievements in the field of self-awareness. The expression of motivation in early youth is professional plans that are motivating in relation to the present. In addition, the main achievement of early adolescence in the formation of motivation is the transformation of an adolescent dream about a future profession into a more realistic, reality-based action plan for one's future professional activity.

The selective motivation of the individual in professional development begins to perform a regulatory function in relation to all manifestations and aspects of the personality of the higher education student, which ensures personal stability, the ability to overcome difficulties, the production of new goals and means of achieving them in the implementation of the already set. There is a stable selective attitude to academic subjects in accordance with the chosen profession. The determination of learning activities by a professional perspective is manifested in all aspects of learning. The involvement of young people in a real professional environment allows them to reveal the qualities that are inherent in a professional, which creates the necessary conditions for choosing a profession. Attitude to work is a significant factor in shaping professional orientation. Ensuring continuity between educational and work activities is central to the formation of the motivational sphere, as well as the primary need of the emerging professional. In early adolescence, the control and evaluation component, which is associated with projecting oneself in the profession, is born. It is expressed in the analysis of the specifics of the conditions of its implementation (professional, social, personal) and its features in relation to the requirements of the profession. The subject's motivation and activity to master the profession are in dialectical unity. Involvement in professional activity changes the tendencies in the emergence of motivation, but the motivation that has already developed determines the success of mastering the future profession and the formation of new personal structures. Among the most important transformations in the motivational sphere of professional development is the trend of increasing the role of intrinsic motivation.

The result of the formation and the basis for further development of motivation is the understanding of one's future profession and oneself in it, the emergence of a certain attitude to one's work, as well as the readiness for active independent activity in the professional field and the desire to improve in the profession. Thus, motivation-driven activity at the stage of professional training is aimed at constructing not only one's practical activity but also oneself as a professional. At the same time, motivation itself becomes a subject of self-education.

Value motivation is the core of the process of professional self-realisation of an individual and determines the main directions of enriching professional experience, further differentiation and integration of the self-concept, and acquisition of new professional knowledge, skills and abilities. Professional development is seen as a long-term progressive process that has

a certain structure and acquires specific content at different age stages. Motivation is an integrative formation that explains the behaviour and actions of a person as a potential or actual subject of work during the period of not only professional but also pre-professional development.

Motivation also acts as a systemic quality, determining the psychological make-up of a person. In fact, motivation expresses the goals for which a person acts, his or her motives and subjective attitude to various aspects of reality.

In the process of mastering the profession, the needs and interests of higher education students arise and are detailed as a result of awareness of professional prospects and an adequate assessment of the inconsistency of requirements for prospects with existing aptitudes, knowledge and skills. In this case, the prospects are a separate goal of the future teacher. Formation and maintenance of sustainable motivation of a higher education student's personality is a special continuous process of matching requirements to prospects through feedback-based activities.

In the context of forming a value-based attitude to future professional activity, motivation is characterised by the motives for choosing a profession and awareness of the peculiarities of future professional activity; positive motivation for learning activities, the need for professional self-improvement; and adequate self-esteem.

The environment in which a person lives is important for motivation: whether this professional environment meets the person's abilities and needs, and whether he or she can fully realise himself or herself in it. To be successful in your profession, to be a highly qualified expert in your field, you must also understand the problems of modern society. In other words, a modern person successfully combines orientations from different spheres of life and work, which allows him or her to respond flexibly to various situations arising in society. Therefore, studying at a pedagogical institution of higher education should ensure such development, which results not only in the formation of orientation towards the profession acquired by future teachers but also in the development of awareness that in order to be successful, it is necessary to have or develop other important moral and social qualities, knowledge, skills, competences.

A value-based attitude to future professional activities is one of the necessary qualities of not only a specialist with a higher education but also a highly moral personality. The future life of today's higher education student depends on which values were prioritised in his or her personal development and what emotions accompanied this process.

The motivation of a value-based attitude towards future professional activity is manifested in positive or negative emotions, which are a direct form of expression of feelings. Emotions and emotionally expressive movements of a person are a product of positive development and play a necessary and important role in regulating his or her activities, including cognitive ones.

The formation of positive motives is successful only if there are feelings, ranging from direct feelings

towards a specific object to higher social feelings related to social values and ideals. The emergence and development of object feelings expresses the formation of a stable emotional attitude [5, p.187].

The moral qualities of a person, to which we also refer the value attitude, have a complex, multifaceted content. This is not a clearly defined and limited group of personal characteristics, so it is impossible to define a specific list of qualities that can be called unconditionally moral.

Modern scholars have proved that moral factors cannot be considered equally with economic, political and other qualities. The personality of a modern professional should be considered in conjunction with his or her moral principles, and strategies, which are of a moral nature, since they are determined by the basic attitude of the subject to the world, people, and himself or herself.

Our understanding of the value-based attitude to future professional activity implies a conscious position on the process and results of this activity for personal and social development. Human behaviour in all spheres of social life – work, life, politics, science, family, personal, collective, international and international relations – is regulated by morality as an essential component of a harmoniously developed personality. Therefore, we consider it necessary to consider the categories of morality and moral education in the context of influencing consciousness in order to form a value-based attitude.

Every human act, every act of communication implies that a person is able to understand their internal problems, to correlate them with his or her own idea of what is right and just, to subordinate them to the voice of his or her own conscience.

Consciousness, in general, is characterised by the ability of a person to distance himself or herself from the existing reality and, through its ideal reflection, to cognise, control and predict the processes that take place in it. Since the need for such awareness and control also affects the person who possesses consciousness, he or she becomes an object of awareness for himself or herself.

One of the forms of social consciousness is moral consciousness, which, like other forms of social consciousness, is a reflection of people's social existence. Moral consciousness includes values, norms, and ideals. Here, morality manifests itself as the pursuit of perfection. Moral consciousness is the spiritual side of morality: norms and principles of behaviour, goals, emotions, feelings, experiences, beliefs, volitional acts and other ideal factors. It is a reflection of people's practical and historical experience in the form of individual and collective ideas, serves as a mechanism of social continuity, regulation and organisation of life, and provides an assessment of the results of individual behaviour.

Successful professional activity of a teacher depends on a number of issues, the solution of which is not always within the scope of acquired university knowledge and skills. Therefore, it is necessary to cultivate such a quality as optimism, which encourages a person to move forward, regardless of circumstances,

improve the initial situation, achieve success and positively evaluate themselves and what has already been achieved, in the context of our study. The establishment of optimism takes place against a social and moral background.

Feelings, like emotions, have their own positive development and, having natural prerequisites, are the product of a person's life in society, communication and education. Since life activity involves overcoming internal and external obstacles, it requires conscious regulation in the form of the will.

In activity, the will performs two interrelated functions: activating and inhibiting. The will is the ability to control one's activities and actively direct them towards achieving one's goals. It represents a special form of not only the ability to achieve something but also the ability to refuse to do anything when it is necessary [4, p. 44]. The will ensures the transition from cognition and human experience to practical activity, to changing reality in connection with the needs, intentions, and interests of a person. With the help of the will, a person organises activities and manages his/her behaviour.

The ability of a person to consciously control himself or herself in activities with difficult-to-achieve goals is a manifestation of will. It implies that a person regulates his or her behaviour, inhibits aspirations and motivations, and organises a series of actions in accordance with consciously set goals. Volitional activity means that a person exercises power over himself, controls his own impulses and, if necessary, suppresses them. The manifestation of the will is a kind of personality activity that is associated with the participation of consciousness in it. Volitional activity necessarily involves a number of acts: assessing the situation; choosing a path for future action; selecting the means necessary to achieve the goal; making a decision, etc.

In a number of cases, volitional activity is associated with making decisions that determine a person's life path and reveal his or her social and moral character. Therefore, the exercise of such volitional efforts is inherent only in a consciously acting personality.

Emotions, like a number of other phenomena, become the subject of human attention when they are hindered in some way. Often, we see emotional factors as the reasons for difficulties in establishing normal relations between an individual and a group [4, p. 67]. And effective teamwork is an integral part of professionalism. According to some researchers, it is emotions that interfere with coping with the task at hand, which is also relevant to professional activities. The author believes that emotional problems are particularly pronounced in people with impaired or weakened ability to effectively self-control.

This condition requires additional efforts to maintain an optimal psychophysiological level, which in turn leads to a number of socio-economic and socio-psychological consequences: increased staff turnover, reduced job satisfaction, deformation of personal and characteristic qualities.

Emotional and volitional resilience is a complex psychological and pedagogical characteristic of personal development, which interconnects volitional

states and volitional qualities that contribute to the implementation of volitional actions by a person in situations of increased emotional tension.

Achieving results in professional activities requires the ability of an individual to subordinate his or her activities and behaviour to socially significant goals. Purposefulness, as a rule, allows a person to achieve a goal in not always favourable circumstances. The activity of a teacher, especially in a pandemic, is accompanied by the ability to control emotions and self-control, which should be nurtured in the student years.

In a general sense, self-organisation is an internal composure that characterises the coherence between the goals of activity and the ways of its implementation. It is manifested in the constant organisation of personal activities and the work of others, the desire to introduce a certain system of organisation into work activities, the improvement of personal work organisation, and protests against disorganisation introduced by any member of the organisation.

The motivation of the process of forming a value-based attitude to professional activity takes place in the educational space of higher education institutions. The effectiveness of this activity of a higher education student depends on interpersonal interaction, in which empathy plays a leading role as the perception of the inner world and emotional state of another person. Empathy is needed to increase productivity, develop competence in communication, and create deeper and more emotional relationships.

Thus, a future professional with a value-based attitude to professional activity should possess a set of qualities that ensure self-regulation of his/her activity and emotional state. In this regard, the motivation of the value attitude of a higher education student to future professional activity is revealed through a set of moral qualities: self-control, organisation, purposefulness, responsibility, optimism, and empathy.

For the successful formation of future teachers' motivation for a value-based attitude to future professional activities, it is important to have a purposeful education as a component of the educational process. With the development of science and the technical basis of production, as well as the complication of social relations, its role is constantly growing. Under modern

conditions, it is impossible to involve a person in life and productive activity without long-term and specially provided education and training. In the educational space of higher education institutions, the education of the individual, the formation of attitudes, and the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities in various fields involve interpersonal interaction. Educational activities will not be successful unless appropriate contact and mutual understanding are established between those involved. Communication is a relevant means of organising educational activities. In other words, personal development and experience acquisition take place both in various types of life activities and in the process of communication. Therefore, the process of forming a positive motivation for the value orientation of the process of mastering the norms of professional communication and behaviour is possible through effective interaction of the subjects of the educational environment of a higher education institution. Moreover, if the interaction is value-based, this condition will contribute to the development and improvement of such a quality as a value-based attitude to future professional activity, characterised by the individual's awareness of the social significance of his or her profession. It is impossible to become a professional, a good specialist in your field without understanding the importance of teaching, its vital importance for society, and interest in it.

References

1. Antonova N. O. Value orientations in the system of personal qualities of students of a higher pedagogical educational institution: Extended abstract of candidate's thesis. Kyiv, 2003. 16 p.
2. Bekh I. D. Spiritual values in personality development. *Pedagogy and psychology*. 2017. No 1. P. 124–129.
3. Boryshevskyi M. Spiritual values in the formation of the individual citizen. *Pedagogy and psychology*. 2007. No 1. P. 147–154.
4. Psychology of personality: dictionary-reference / Ed. P. Gornostai, T. Tytarenko. Kyiv: Ruta, 2001. 320 p.
5. Zaniuk S. S. Psychology of motivation: education manual. Kyiv: Lybid, 2009. 304 p.